

Deliverable 1.1

Tools and training for setting up a transformative network

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Introduction

Global challenges can only be solved by true collaboration between stakeholders and individuals in a networked environment. FIT4FOOD2030 supports the urgently needed transformation of research and innovation (R&I) on Food and Nutrition Security (FNS) in Europe. To achieve that, FIT4FOOD2030 will create a sustainable, multi-stakeholder platform, mobilizing a wide variety of stakeholders at the level of cities, regions, countries, and Europe wide. Known as the FOOD2030 Platform, this network will make R&I policies on FNS more coherent, build competences of current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers and society at large, and raise awareness around FOOD 2030.

The three inter-linked structures of the FOOD2030 Platform are:

- **EU think tank:** the link between the EC and Member States & Associated Countries, with a global outreach;
- **Policy Labs** to increase and align public/private R&I policies/programs on FNS, building on and expanding existing national/regional networks; and
- **City Labs** to develop/pilot action-oriented trainings for students, consumers, researchers and professionals linking Science Centers/Science Shops to networks of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact cities.

How to use this guide

This 'Tools and Training for Setting up a Transformative Network' deliverable is designed to support FIT4FOOD2030 Policy and City Lab coordinators in developing a sustainable network that has transformative capacities for R&I on FNS. This deliverable provides a series of training modules that cover the essential elements of setting up a transformative network. Each module presents (example) exercises, followed by resources to gather background information on the module-topic and/or resources to (re-)design alternative exercises. The resource pictures and underscored texts are hyperlinked.

The exercises in each module are written down in such a way that Policy and City Lab coordinators can apply them:

- Individually or with their own team, e.g. for setting up their Lab,
- Within City and Policy Labs, in order to mobilize (a transformative network of) change-makers in (policy-making for) R&I on FNS. In other words, we encourage Lab coordinators to do the exercises during the events that they organize in their Labs.

Policy and City Lab coordinators may recognize most exercises from the first training session of FIT4FOOD2030 (February 2018, Amsterdam). When Lab coordinators intend to apply the exercises in their own Lab sessions, they may need to (1) select and put this selection of exercises in a meaningful sequence and (2) slightly adapt the exercises for context-specific circumstances (e.g. participant knowledge and skills levels). When applying multiple exercises in a row during Lab events, we highly recommend event coordinators to take a facilitating role, or ask an external facilitator to guide the activities where necessary. We encourage building-in moments for the plenary exchange or collection of questions, concerns and ideas, as well as a moment for (individual) reflection, e.g. by means of journaling¹.

¹ For example, session participants can report in a notebook answers to questions like 'What did I get out of this exercise?', 'What caught my attention?', 'What did I (not) like?', 'What does this exercise mean for my work?', etc. More fundamental questions can be found in the resources on [journaling](#) in this Deliverable.

Note on facilitation expertise

In case coordinators decide to use the modules' exercises during their Lab events, certain facilitation expertise is required. The table below provides an overview of this:

	Skills-level	Explanation
Module 1: FIT4FOOD2030		
Exercise A: FIT4FOOD2030	Intermediate	FIT4FOOD2030 project specific knowledge is useful
Exercise B: Transformation	Intermediate	Knowledge of system transformation is useful
Module 2: Strategizing a transformative network		
Exercise A: Stakeholder analysis	Beginner / intermediate	Experience in doing stakeholder analysis is useful but not essential
Exercise B: Lab strategies	Beginner / intermediate	Experience in network forming can come in handy
Module 3: Building a transformative network		
Exercise A: Preparing for communication with stakeholders	Beginner / intermediate	Experience in creative thinking can be useful
Exercise B: Designing a communication strategy	Beginner / intermediate	Experience in emailing / writing to (unknown) stakeholders can be useful
Exercise C: Connecting transformation to individual drives	Intermediate	Advanced communication can be useful
Module 4: Transformative skills		
Exercise A: Deep listening	Beginner / intermediate	Knowledge of listening levels can be useful
Exercise B: Visioning food system transformation	Beginner / intermediate	Knowledge of the food system can be handy, but is not essential (if template pictures are used)
Exercise C: Visioning food (systems) R&I transformation	Beginner / intermediate	Knowledge of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) can be useful
Exercise D: Visioning own actions	Intermediate	Creative facilitation and meditation guiding skills can be handy
Exercise E: Learning and Reflection	Intermediate	Experience of facilitating learning & reflection (e.g. in a different contexts) can be handy

Note that it could be useful to get an external facilitator on board in Lab events, so that coordinators can observe and function as rapporteur. In case there are resources to organize events hosted by multiple facilitators, it can be wise to divide and/or alternate tasks. One facilitator takes the lead in introducing (particular) exercises and moderating conversations (in case plenary), another/the other facilitators could take the role of a rapporteur, so that conversation content is recorded in a structured way.

Lastly, it may be interesting to ask participants of Lab event to prepare materials before the event takes place. This can 'probe' their thinking on FNS, food systems, transformation, etc. Example homework tasks could be to bring along pictures/photos of food systems elements, challenges, and opportunities. In this deliverable, the food system transformation visioning exercise of module 4 makes use of such preparatory homework.

Abbreviations

- DLA – Dynamic Learning Agenda
- FNS – Food and Nutrition Security
- R&I – Research and Innovation
- RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation

Module 1: FIT4FOOD2030 & transformation

Introduction

FIT4FOOD2030 aspires to transform research and innovation (R&I) on Food Nutrition and Security (FNS). This module provides a description of the FIT4FOOD2030 project details. The information is essential for Policy and City Lab coordinators to be aware of, but can be of use as well in Lab communications, e.g. for e-mails or during events and activities with stakeholder groups or individuals. The resources accompanying this module link to FIT4FOOD2030's foundation: FOOD 2030, food systems, transformation, and RRI.

Exercise A: FIT4FOOD2030

Objective: To develop an overview of FIT4FOOD2030.

The FIT4FOOD2030 quick facts in a row are as follows:

- The FIT4FOOD2030 tag line is *'Towards FOOD 2030 – future-proofing the European food systems through Research & Innovation'*.
- The project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) to help the European Commission to implement FOOD 2030, the EU Research & Innovation (R&I) policy framework for Food and Nutrition Security in Europe (FNS).
- FOOD 2030 ultimately aspires for R&I that 'future-proofs' the European Food System.
- Future proof means (FOOD 2030):
 - **Sustainable:** with respect to natural resource scarcity and in respect of planetary boundaries.
 - **Resilient:** with respect to adapting to climate and global change, including extreme events and migration;
 - **Responsible:** with respect to being ethical, transparent and accountable;
 - **Diverse:** with respect to being open to a wide range of technologies, practices, approaches, cultures and business models;
 - **Competitive:** with respect to providing jobs and growth;
 - **Inclusive:** with respect to engaging all food system actors, including civil society, fighting food poverty, and providing healthy food for all.
- To future-proof food systems FOOD 2030 identifies four key R&I priorities (Ibid):
 - **NUTRITION** for sustainable and healthy diets: Ensuring that nutritious food and water is available, accessible and affordable for all, reducing hunger, ensuring high levels of food safety, reducing the incidence of diet-related diseases, and helping all citizens to adopt sustainable and healthy diets.
 - **CLIMATE** smart and environmentally sustainable food systems: Building climate smart food systems adaptive to climate change, conserving natural resources and contributing to climate change mitigation. It seeks to support healthy, productive and biodiverse ecosystems. Ensuring diversity in food systems including in terms of cultural and environmental diversity.
 - **CIRCULARITY** and resource efficiency of food systems: Implementing resource-efficient circular economy principles across the whole food system while reducing its

environmental footprint. Circularity is applied for sustainable and resource-efficient food systems and food losses and waste are minimized throughout.

- **INNOVATION** and empowerment of communities: Boosting innovation and investment, while empowering communities. A broad innovation ecosystem leading to new business models and value-added products, goods and services, meeting the needs, values and expectations of society in a responsible way.
- FOOD 2030 identifies that current R&I practice is not adequate to meet the challenges facing the food systems (environmental challenges, health challenges and resource challenges). Factors hindering current R&I include:
 - R&I is currently a fragmented landscape of separated disciplines and sectors both regarding its policy and scientific dimension. It has successfully dealt with individual compartmentalized parts of the food system such as agriculture, food safety and nutrition, but rarely takes an integrated perspective.
 - Low levels of active involvement of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), users (e.g. farmers), consumers and citizens. Many researchers and policy makers barely value the knowledge of users and do not know how to organize stakeholder interactions during the research process.
 - Academic incentive structures and R&I funding programs often do not support the use of inter- and transdisciplinary research approaches.
 - Private sector R&I investments are modest.
 - Many member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) fund research mainly through open calls instead of system-oriented calls, making it more challenging to establish R&I priorities for FNS.
 - Appropriate tools and incentives are needed to support an innovation culture both within R&I policy programs, and food related policies and regulations.
 - Increased communication and training on the impact and value of R&I is needed to foster the paradigm shifts and for investments towards FNS.
 - There are two key approaches that FIT4FOOD2030 seeks to embed within R&I practice around FNS: a food systems approach and Responsible Research and Innovation.
 - **A Food Systems Approach** considers the entire value chain of food from inputs, production, storage, distribution, consumer intake and waste streams. It involves an awareness of the food system from farm to fork to gut. There is also an appreciation of the complex interlinkages between social, economic and environmental factors.
 - **Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)** is a different conception of research and innovation where all stakeholders are involved in the R&I practice and share responsibility for the outcomes. RRI activities bring together and align a wide range of actors and activities involved in R&I processes towards desirable, sustainable and acceptable future outcomes. The key aspects of RRI practice are as follows:
 - **Diverse & inclusive:** involving a wide range of actors in R&I practice, deliberation, and decision-making to foster more societally useful knowledge.
 - **Anticipative & reflective:** reflecting on the underlying assumptions, values, and motives to better understand how R&I shapes the future.
 - **Open & transparent:** communicating in a balanced, meaningful way through methods, results, conclusions, to enable public scrutiny and dialogue. This benefits the visibility and understanding of R&I.
 - **Responsive & adaptive to change:** being able to modify modes of thought and behavior, and adapt overarching organizational structures in response to changing circumstances, knowledge, and perspectives.

RRI additionally requires that specific attention is paid to public engagement, gender equality, ethics, science education and open access.

- FIT4FOOD2030 will integrate RRI and a Food Systems approach in to current R&I practice by building the FOOD2030 Platform, a transformative network which will connect stakeholders at multiple levels (cities/regions, countries, and Europe). This will work towards making Research & Innovation (R&I) policies on Food and Nutrition Security (FNS) more coherent, to build the competences of current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers, and society at large, and raise awareness of FOOD 2030.
- The three inter-linked structures of the FIT4FOOD2030 platform are:
 - **EU think tank** to act as a link between the EC and Member States & Associated Countries, with a global outreach
 - **Policy Labs** to increase and align public/private R&I policies/programs on FNS, building on and expanding existing national/regional networks; and
 - **City Labs** to develop/pilot action-oriented trainings for students, consumers, researchers and professionals linking Science Centers/Science Shops to networks of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact cities.
- Lab coordinators are assigned to build these transformative networks in a local context. Activities within the labs will follow the following phases:
 - 1. Actor identification & mobilization, visioning, and system understanding:** The first phase involves identifying and mobilizing relevant actors within each lab. It involves developing and aligning visions amongst these actors and gaining an increased understanding of barriers and opportunities for transforming the current system.
 - 2. Pathways development:** during phase two transformation agendas will be developed by identifying showcases – initiatives that have contributed, or are contributing, to food systems R&I developments – in food systems R&I and exploring potential breakthroughs – a significant achievement that may lead towards a step change or radical change of the food system, making it more sustainable and resilient.
 - 3. Action planning and training:** the third phase involves putting into practice the new lab transformation agendas. Labs will engage in the prototyping and piloting of innovative experiments.
 - 4. Scaling up and continuity:** the project starts with 7 Policy Labs and 7 City Labs across Europe in year 1, and expands to 10 Policy Labs and 14 City Labs throughout the project. In addition, FIT4FOOD2030 will develop instruments (Tools and Guidelines) which will be distributed through existing R&I policy collaboration initiatives.

These quick facts are summarized in [FIT4FOOD2030 template slides](#). The original PowerPoint presentation can be found on [Edugroepen](#). We usually use more jargon than we think, so in communicating about FIT4FOOD2030 it is useful to be aware of the (automated) use of jargon (and abbreviations like R&I, RRI, FNS, etc.).

Exercise B: Transformation

Objective: To understand what food system transformation implies from a more generic, system transformation perspective.

Transforming a system requires change on multiple levels, for example:

- Change in (mostly more visible) behaviors and actions of actors in the system,
- Change on institutional level and in governance,
- Change in power hierarchies and distribution of responsibilities,
- Change in underlying structures, beliefs, values and assumptions.

It may be apparent that realizing such transformation takes several decades.

The Iceberg model (see Fig. 1) shows the multi-level change required for system transformation in a comprehensive way.

Figure 1: The Iceberg model

In a system transformation perspective, citizens are no longer (only) seen as *users* of the system, in other words, ‘consumer’, or *choosers*, in other words ‘consumers with preferences’. In a system transformation, all actors are collectively responsible for the realization of change. From that perspective, citizens are *shapers* and change makers of the (new) system, just as all professional stakeholders are.

Strategies for transformation are multi-faceted, and include:

- Creating coherence between actors, by identifying and developing shared meanings and common values.
- Developing a compelling narrative (preferable collectively) as a ‘shared (metaphorical) model for change’.
- Innovation policy mixes with regime destabilizing and niche creating functions².

These strategies require face-to-face contact between actors, either individually or by means of group meetings. Module 2 on ‘Strategizing a transformative network’, Module 3 on ‘Building a transformative network’ and Module 4 on ‘Transformation skills building’, provide support in mobilizing transformative networks.

We recommend that coordinators become familiar with system transformation thinking, as well as making this thinking clear to the actors that attend Lab events/meetings. The resources of this module provide links to more in-depth information on (food) system transformation, in addition to resources on FOOD 2030 and RRI.

² The Sussex Policy Research Unit published a useful briefing note on Designing Innovation Policy for Transformative Change, which provides an overview of the innovation policy mixes (in chapter 2) with two types of functions and policy measures.

Resources: FIT4FOOD2030 & transformation

Topic	Link	Explanation
FNS & FOOD 2030		<u>FOOD 2030</u> was launched on the World Food day in October 2016 (following the 2015 Milan World Expo). Food and Nutrition Security (FNS) is defined as (European Commission): “Ensuring that everybody is able to access sufficient, sustainable, affordable, healthy and nutritious food in the short and long term”.
Food systems		What is a food system? This <u>Food source chapters-website</u> offers online modules introducing challenges to the food system, linking various perspectives.
Food system transformation thinking		What would a transformation in food systems involve? This is <u>video provides a comprehensive introduction into food system transformation thinking</u> .
Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)		What is RRI? The <u>RRI-tools website</u> offers an RRI-toolkit with guidelines, methods, tools and tips on RRI. On this website, amongst others, more specific training modules can be found for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <u>Education partners</u> ○ <u>Policy makers</u> For example, there are <u>open source training modules about the concept of RRI</u> and how to apply it
Transformation – Theory U		What is transformation? This <u>EdX course on 'Theory U'</u> by MIT, teaches the core principles of inciting transformation. <u>Otto Scharmer's book on Theory U</u> describes the steps, skills and processes required to realize a transformation.

Module 2: Strategizing a transformative network

Introduction

In order to successfully build a transformative network it is necessary to gain an understanding of who should be involved and how.

- In terms of 'who', stakeholder-mapping exercises are essential. Where do which groups talk about FNS and/or R&I? Who are the key actors to realize transformation in R&I on FNS? Who stands to win or lose from the aspired change? And what are the power relations between actors? Therefore, who are the crucial actors to involve in your network?
- In terms of the 'how', it is essential to think about the form of the transformative network. Should the Policy or City Lab be a new network? Or should it merely function as a connector of multiple existing networks? Or somewhere in-between?

This module provides (a) exercises for identifying and mapping stakeholders, and (b) an introduction and exercise for designing a transformative network (e.g. your lab strategy). Both exercises are useful activities to undertake in the following cases:

- Individually, as a Lab coordinator, to define and take a role as a change maker. In this case, the exercises can be used in the preparation phase of the lab activities. However, note that it is desirable to continuously update stakeholder databases and the lab strategy in order to realize the aspired FIT4FOOD2030 objectives in three years.
- With individual or multiple stakeholders during Lab events. In such cases, the exercises function as tools to make the process of designing the transformative network inclusive, while enabling Lab stakeholders/participants to define and take a role as change maker too.

The resources of this module provide links to mapping and transformative network strategizing exercises.

Exercise A: Stakeholder analysis

Objective: To become familiarized with tools for system and stakeholder analysis and to strategize around actor mobilization.

A commonly used description for stakeholder is: *An individual, group of individuals, or organization that is affected by- or influences the realization of visions or aims of a particular organization or process* (note this is not an official definition). Roughly speaking, stakeholders can be classified in the following groups, though this is not exhaustive:

- Government
- Education
- Business (profit)
- Non-governmental / non-profit organizations
- Societal interest groups
- Individual citizens.

This classification can function as a useful checklist when undertaking a stakeholder mapping exercise.

With this list in mind, the following questions are crucial:

- What are the stakeholder groups relating to (R&I on) FNS, food systems or food in your country/region?
- Who are the most essential stakeholders for realizing a transformation in R&I on FNS (in your country/region), without whom you cannot succeed? Create a hierarchy of importance in the created stakeholders/groups list.
- For each stakeholder/group, how you would ideally want to include/involve/engage them?

To describe each stakeholder, it can be useful to use a [stakeholder analysis template](#).

Note that it is crucial to discuss the mapping with others, either to see whether particular stakeholders are overlooked, or to justify/falsify assumptions taken regarding their characteristics.

Exercise B: Lab strategies

Objective: To strategize one's own role in mobilizing actors for a transformative network.

In building a transformative network, coordinators will undoubtedly play a key role in driving the development of the network. The idea is that eventually each Lab converts into a self-sustaining network. Self-sustaining means 'the network keeps itself going', but it is important to consider what 'self-sustaining' would look like for each Lab (beyond the activities described in the FIT4FOOD2030 project). Picturing this will help you to build towards this picture from the outset. 'Self-sustainability' will mean something different to Policy Labs and City Labs, and even be City Lab-dependent (Science Shop and Science Museums/Center are different).

Therefore, for each Lab, it is important to contemplate the following considerations either as coordinator(s) or with the (first engaged) stakeholders together:

1. What is the starting level in local context?

Option 1: (Operate in a) Well-established network

- Advantages
 - Lots of momentum to build on
 - Potentially a bigger impact within 3 years
- Disadvantages/challenges
 - More time needed to get to know the network
 - Finding how you 'fit in': who are the right people and how do you get in?
 - Potential perceived notion of competitiveness

Option 2: (Operate in a) Less-established network

- Advantages
 - Easier to get to know what exists
 - Chance to play a greater role in shaping the network
 - Potentially there is a greater need
- Disadvantages/challenges
 - More time on initial identification of actors, creating connections
 - Less chance of building momentum

2. What is the desired / practically possible network configuration and how this may change over time?

The configuration of your network will depend on your local context and on your decisions about the involvement of specific stakeholders (and their networks).

- A first simplified possible network configuration is a network in which a Lab coordinator connects to a variety of new stakeholders. It is a quite centralized network with the Lab as core.
- A second simplified possible network configuration is that the Lab coordinator connects to certain stakeholders who already have their established networks. It might be possible to form a core group with some of the contact persons of specific networks. In such configurations, there are stakeholders in the network that are not directly connected to the Lab coordinator.
- A third simplified possible network configuration is a network in which all stakeholders are interconnected, meaning different networks are brought together. This is a more scattered and distributed network than the first two networks. The Lab coordinator is not necessarily core of the network.

3. What and how will decision-making (on what issues) take place?

- This question depends upon the configuration of your lab. For example, you might take certain decisions yourself or, if you have a core group of stakeholders, it may encourage greater ownership of the lab by them if you take decisions together.

Resources: Strategizing a transformative network

Topic	Link	Explanation
Stakeholder analysis tools		The mind-tools website offers a comprehensive guide into (generic) stakeholder analysis, including templates for i.e. power-interest graphs.
Stakeholder engagement tools in food context		More specific for food systems context, the Food & Business Knowledge Platform provides an interesting overview of stakeholder mapping and engagement as well.
Communities of Practice		What are communities of practice (CoP) and how to facilitate co-creation between them? This guide of Regeer & Bunders (2003) provides an overview.

Module 3: Building a transformative network

Introduction

Once you have successfully identified and analyzed who your key stakeholders are and the basic architecture for connecting them, it is necessary to think about how you will communicate and engage with these stakeholders in a more practical sense. An important element is to build a deep connection with and between stakeholders that are desired in the transformative network. This module introduces three exercises to support that:

- A preparation exercise that supports thinking about stakeholders and building empathy for them before getting in touch. This exercise can eventually help to tailor communication with stakeholders.
- A communication strategy exercise that supports the design of tailor-made, efficient and effective communication with the set of stakeholders desired in a transformative network.
- A connection exercise that can help to unravel the deep drives, motivations and identities of individuals. Ideally, transformative networks emerge from and connect to the drives, motivations and identities of involved stakeholders. Hence by diving into deeper notions, engaging stakeholders in a transformative network can become sustainable (enduring).

The exercises are useful for Lab coordinators themselves, as well as for participants of a Lab, when coordinators mobilize them to expand the transformative network. This module's resources will explore in more detail different ways to go about this.

Exercise A: Preparing for communication with stakeholders

Objective: To develop empathy for the various stakeholders to be engaged in a transformative network

This exercise uses the creation of a Persona as a method for 'empathizing'. A Persona is a fictitious person that 'summarizes' existing individuals with particular characteristics. A Persona's purpose is to create a connection between the Persona-creator and the Persona. This differs from thinking in stereotypes, of which the purpose is more to classify people, sometimes combined with humor or a cynical note. It can be helpful to make Personas of various actors to support the development of an effective multi-stakeholder communication and engagement strategy.

Using the [Persona-template](#), Persona creation comprises of the following steps:

- First, choose one actor who you are the least familiar with (or two in case this actor group is highly variable). Make a Persona of this actor by means filling out the template. Make this persona in such a way that you could feel a connection with them. Avoid taking a cynical stance towards this persona while making it.
- Write a letter / email (or create any other mean) to communicate with this persona.
- Reflect on the following:
 - What would you tell her/him about your intended activities on transforming (R&I around) food systems?
 - What life interests or motives of the persona can you appeal to?
 - What would you 'ask from' him/her?
 - In what way could the communication be more specifically oriented to this Persona in particular?

To justify/falsify the Persona, it can be useful to engage in a connection exercise with stakeholders that feel the most distant from your own network /position/context.

Exercise B: Designing a communication strategy

Objective: To develop a strategy for tailor-made communication with various stakeholders.

Especially when it comes to multi-stakeholder events or processes, it is recommendable to operationalize the steps towards the (first) event with the help of the 5W+H principle (who, when, why, what, where, how). Figure 2 below is an example matrix that can be used to design a communicating plan for (personal) stakeholder communication, a (multi-) stakeholder event or process, with specific attention to tailoring the communication with regard to each stakeholder separately.

WHO?	WHEN?	WHY? (OBJECTIVE)	HOW? (CHANNEL)	WHAT? (MESSAGE)

The following steps can help to create a communication plan:

- With your stakeholder analysis and Persona(s) in mind, make a timeline with an overview of ‘who to contact when, with which means, to what goal, with which message’, etc.
- Write a letter to one stakeholder first. How do you introduce your connection with them? What information do you provide? What is the action you ask from this stakeholder? With this letter as a template, create letters for all the other stakeholders in the list. Adjust jargon and message sequence accordingly.
- Let one other person read the letter(s) before using it.
- Think about how to keep actor(s) ‘on board’ once connected and contacted.

Exercise C: Connecting to individual drives

Objective: To create a connection between personal drives and transformation.

The idea of this exercise is to meet a (new) person with who(m) a connection is desirable, e.g. for the expansion of your network.

Take this person for a walk, e.g. outside in a green area. Either interview this person, or engage in a dialogue about the following questions:

- Who am I / why are you?
- Why am I doing my work / why are you doing your work? (work motivation)
- What would I / you need to fully realize my / your work motivation?

It is advisable to let one person speak at a time; the listener does not necessarily have to ask questions. This allows more openness for what is actually being said (and little worries about which follow-up questions to pose). Furthermore, it is advisable to both look in the same direction / in front of you (and not in each other's eyes), to literally look at 'the future'.

In case of rain, place two chairs in front of a window with a good view, and look outside (so you do not look in each other's eyes).

This exercise can also be done as a self-reflection exercise, e.g. by journaling for yourself. Such reflection can help change makers to keep their transformative network activities/ actions connected to themselves.

Resources: Building a transformative network

Topic	Explanation
5W + H	Various <u>companies</u> , <u>platforms</u> and <u>consultants</u> emphasize the importance of careful stakeholder communication, and the usefulness of the 5W+H principle in particular (Who? When? Why? How? What?). Ideally the communication goals are defined as <u>SMART objectives</u> .
Journaling (Theory U)	Journaling (widely promoted in the <u>Theory U course and sourcebook</u>) can also be done on the following reflective questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Over the past days and weeks, what did you notice about your (emerging) self? 2. Who have been your "Guardian Angels" (helpers) in your life's journey so far? 3. Crack: Where do you feel the future in your life and work right now? 4. Frustration: What about your current work and/or personal life frustrates you the most? 5. Happiness: What are your most important sources of energy and happiness in your life and work? 6. Helicopter: Watch yourself from above (as if in a helicopter). What are you doing? What are you trying to do in this stage of your professional and personal journey? Helicopter II: Watch your collective journey from above: what are you trying to do collectively in the present stage of your collective journey? 7. Question: Given the above, what Questions do you now need to ask yourself? 8. Listen to your young self: Look at your current situation from the viewpoint of you as a

-
- young person, at the beginning of your journey: What does that young person have to say to you?
9. Footprint: Imagine you could fast-forward to the very last moments of your life, when it is time for you to pass on. Now look back on your life's journey as a whole. What would you want to see at that moment? What footprint do you want to leave behind on the planet?
 10. From that future point of view: What advice have you given to your current self?
 11. Now return again to the present and crystallize what it is that you want to create: your vision and intention for the next 3-5 years. What vision and intention do you have for yourself and your work? What are some essential core elements of the future that you want to create in your personal, professional, and social life? Describe or draw as concretely as possible the images and elements that occur to you.
 12. Feel the connection of our global U.Lab community that is present across the planet in this moment: What is our collective highest future possibility? What could we be an instrument for? What could we collectively create within the next 3-5 years?
 13. Letting-go: What would you have to let go of in order to bring your vision into reality? What is the old stuff that must die? What is the old skin (behaviors, assumptions, etc.) that you need to shed?
 14. Prototyping: Over the next three months, if you were to prototype a microcosm of the future in which you could discover "the new" by doing something, what would that prototype look like?
 15. People: Who can help you make your highest future possibilities a reality? Who might be your core helpers and partners?
 16. Action: If you were to take on the project of bringing your intention into reality, what practical first steps would you take over the next 3 days?
-

Module 4: Transformation skills building

Introduction

This module focuses on the more practical skills that Lab coordinators and stakeholders need for to form a resilient transformative network. The suggested exercises largely build on principles of Theory U. System transformation requires people to be engaged in a transformation process, from analyzing the current situation to defining and taking actions towards a desired future. Theory U-based exercises largely focus on the inclusion of people's motivations and drives in such system analysis and action defining for transformation. Thereby they invoke a personal engagement in transformation, and make people change makers in an intuitive and authentic manner. The exercises of this module help change makers in the following way:

- **Exercise A** on 'deep listening builds on Theory U's principles of communication with the 'mind', 'hearth' and 'will' (Scharmer & Kaufer, 2018), and the self-monitoring of this (journaling). Especially the communication on the level of the 'will' helps actors of a transformative network to create connections between one another, as well as between themselves (their own drives and goals) and the (actions of the) transformative network.
- **Exercise B** on 'visioning food system transformation' aligns with Theory U's (a) intuitive analysis of a current (undesired) situation and (b) the prototyping of desired futures.
- **Exercise C** on 'visioning transformation in R&I on FNS' and exercise D on 'visioning own actions', builds on the prototyping principle as well. The former is more related to medium to long-term impact (3-10 years), whereas the latter focused on shorter-term achievements (< 3 years).
- **Exercise D** on 'visioning own actions' moves from a vision of the future towards imagining action.
- **Exercise E** on 'learning and reflection' has a link with the journaling practice of Theory U. Yet the provided tasks build on the Dynamic Learning Agenda methodology. The DLA methodology is supportive to the practical realization of transformation, e.g. for monitoring and to make the network perform to its full (collective) potential.

All exercises are useful for Lab coordinators as well as for the stakeholders of events that Lab coordinators may organize.

Exercise A: Deep listening

Objective: To enhance familiarity with deep listening principles in a low-threshold manner.

Creating a good connection between actors of a transformative network is essential to realizing true transformation in our surroundings through our actions (Theory U). One important tool for creating connections is 'deep listening'. Roughly speaking, four levels of listening can be identified in the interactions between people, of which the last level is the most beneficial to incite transformation (ibid):

- **Downloading:** Listening from your own habits and to what you already know, in order to reconfirm this. We usually notice ourselves saying or thinking 'of course', 'right', and 'ahuh' in this level of listening.
- **Factual listening:** Noting new information that differs from what you already know/expect. This can be noticed when you think 'oh?', or 'really?'
- **Empathizing:** Listening from the other person's perspective and feeling an emotional connection. Key reactions on this level are 'ahhww, poor you!', or 'yeah, super nice!'.

- **Generative listening:** Connecting to an emerging future and possibilities that link to who you really are. On this level, excitement in terms of ‘wow!’ or new visions of the person you are talking with, or new visions of yourself, may arise.

The following exercise embraces the listening principles of Theory U and helps people to train in generative listening.

Pair with somebody you have not or hardly spoken with so far. Engage in a conversation on ideas about your personal role in changing R&I on FNS³. One party of the conversation takes the lead in speaking; after ±5-10 min the other person takes a turn to speak. Best is to look at a point on the horizon (not at each other). After finishing this, use the [listening self-observation template](#) to monitor your listening skills. Repeat this exercise and monitor your listening once in a while. Try to train yourself towards generative listening in particular. You may notice a change over time in your questioning style as well.

Exercise B: Visioning food system transformation

Objective: To develop a broad understanding of the food system, and to collectively create a vision of (a) the food system and its elements, and (b) the desired transformation in order to set the scene for later discussions (e.g. on R&I).

FIT4FOOD2030 focuses on transforming Research and Innovation (R&I) around food and nutrition security (FNS). But what exactly is ‘transformation’? And what do we mean with food systems, a food system approach, and transformation in that system? The exercise below allows people to intuitively analyse the food system, its challenges and its opportunities, and the required transformation.

Take a range of photographs/pictures depicting elements of the food system and its challenges and opportunities. Alternatively, ask people to bring photographs / pictures of food system elements, challenges and opportunities to a meeting (preferred picture size: ± 4 pictures on an A4).

Go through the following tasks:

- What are the basic elements of the food system? Use the pictures/photos of the food system and make clusters of all photos/pictures.
 - What are the relations between the different elements?
 - Is anything missing or underrepresented?
- Where (in) do you see the current food system ‘dying’? Use the pictures/photos of challenges in food systems to collectively depict the answer.
- Where (in) do you see ‘new seeds’ being planted, which (would) result in a rebirth of the food system? Use the pictures/photos of challenges in food systems to collectively depict the answer.

The visioning is not necessarily about ‘positioning pictures on a table and clustering them’, but more about the conversation and exchange of ideas that arise while doing the exercise. So frequently ask one another WHY particular pictures are positioned in a particular spot, and what the picture means to everybody. A rapporteur can take notes of this exercise to report on the main thoughts that are being shared.

Once done, engage in a dialogue around the following question:

³ Note that many other conversation topics can be chosen to practice the various levels of listening.

- Considering the envisioned ‘challenges’ and the ‘desired food system’, how do we get to the ‘desired food system’?

Exercise C: Visioning transformation in R&I on FNS

Objective: To create an individual (and/or collective) vision of the eventual impact e.g. of (collective) transformative actions on R&I into FNS.

Envision the way you see your short-term impact on R&I into FNS, individually, in clay. Everything is possible and allowed. When ready, enter in a dialogue about the various created ‘clay impact visions’. Make sense of the variety that may have arisen, identify commonalities and differences. Based on individual ideas, envision a commonly desired impact e.g. on a flip chart (keywords, drawings).

Exercise D: Visioning own actions

Objective: To envisage one’s own activities in relation to changing R&I on FNS.

Meditation or daydreaming can help to imagine new routines. In this exercise you imagine a day in the life of researcher/teacher/innovator working for a food company/policy maker/‘ordinary’ citizen, in three years, in relation to a transformation in R&I on FNS.

What does (s)he look like? How does (s)he wake up? Where does (s)he go to during the day? What does that place look like? With whom does (s)he get in touch during the day? What do they converse about or work on? When does (s)he end the (work)day? How does (s)he travel home? What are his/her reflections on the day? Etc.

It can help to ask somebody else to read these questions while you close your eyes. An example of a more extensive meditation text can be found in the [templates section](#).

After having contemplated on these questions, do the following:

- What have you seen? Draw it on an A3 sheet.
- Discuss the drawings with others, to discover the following things:
 - In what way are the visions different or similar?
 - What challenges, concerns, or fears do you foresee/feel in realizing this vision?
 - What does this vision imply for your upcoming activities (e.g. tomorrow)?
 - Finalize this exercise by a discussion about the key insights gained during this exercise.

Exercise E: Learning and Reflection

Objective: To elicit learning desires in order to create a Dynamic Learning Agenda concerning transformative network building / transforming R&I on FNS.

Changing R&I on FNS involves challenges that are not always easy to address. In essence being part of a transformative platform is a continuous learning process. It is recommended to make this learning very explicit, e.g. by facilitating reflection exercises that allow to unpick the problems and find how we can use our agency to tackle them. The Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA) is a methodology to bring learning and reflection to the fore by generating learning questions that can be continually referred to. The exercise below is an example of a DLA activity. The accompanying

resources below link to the [DLA methodology](#) and provide more inspiration for learning & reflection exercises.

Define a vision regarding what you want to achieve in transforming R&I on FNS.

Think about the following questions:

- What are your greatest worries?
- What fills you with excitement?
- Why is the current situation not yet achieving your vision? Think of barriers at a system level.

The following aspects of a system may assist you in identifying the barriers:

- The knowledge infrastructure: e.g. education/knowledge/research
 - The physical infrastructure: e.g. transport/distance.
 - Legislation and regulation: e.g. technical standards, employment legislation or the legal framework.
 - Values, norms and symbols: e.g. the political and economic climate and the culture of a country, region or sector, and to social norms and values.
 - Social interaction between actors: this can be too intensive, meaning that the actors' relationships become so tightly intertwined that nobody can take the first step, and their view of reality will be distorted; it can also be too loose and too narrow in scope, so that people are unaware of each other's visions.
 - The market structure: e.g. system barriers and opportunities that arise due to a range of market phenomena such as monopoly, oligopoly, supply and demand.
- Discuss these barriers and cluster them into themes.
 - Choose three of the most significant barriers and formulate a learning question for each of them. Use the following construction to define a learning question:
“What can I/WE do to achieve our vision/aim given that these barriers and/or opportunities exist?”

Use the following to start imagining your approach to these questions:

Imagine a future where the worries on the post-its no longer exist. Answer the following questions:

- How far in the future are you now?
- What has happened?
- What sort of barriers have been overcome on the way (system)?
- Which resources were activated/mobilized?
- How did you contribute to the solution?

Fill out the [DLA diary \(template\)](#). This can be used periodically to ensure that learning and reflection is integrated into the transformation process.

Resources: Transformation skills

Topic	Link	Explanation
Listening levels		<p>This video of the Theory U course on EdX (login may be required) explains the various levels of listening in more detail. Other useful communication principles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-violent communication • Humble inquiry • Appreciative inquiry.
Facilitating deep listening / dialogue		<p>This guide of Chris Corrigan pays extensive attention to the 'internal world' of meeting hosts, in order to realize true listening and dialogue among event participants.</p>
Visioning futures / creative thinking		<p>An Open University A to Z guide on creativity techniques, categorized by different stages of problem solving.</p>
Visioning futures / creative thinking		<p>The method section of the design company IDEO is by far the most famous guide on creative techniques. Not only for generating (design) solutions, but especially also for creative problem analysis.</p>
Dynamic Learning Agenda Method (DLA)		<p>The Dynamic Learning Agenda is comprehensively described in this DLA publication. In the appendix we added a DLA template (customized for FIT4FOOD2030)</p>
Learning & Reflection		<p>Here you can find more inspiration for learning and reflection exercises: WUR guide on making learning & reflection more explicit.</p>

Templates

FIT4FOOD2030 template slides

Introducing FIT4FOOD2030
'Towards FOOD 2030 - future-proofing the European food systems through Research & Innovation'

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 774688

FIT4FOOD2030
'Towards FOOD 2030 - future-proofing the European food systems through Research & Innovation'

The FIT4FOOD2030 project supports the EC to implement FOOD 2030 – the EU Research & Innovation (R&I) policy framework for Food and Nutrition Security in Europe

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 774688 www.fit4food2030.eu #FOOD2030EU

Background: Food 2030

On World Food day in October 2016, the EC launched Food 2030 (following the 2015 Milan World Expo)

Food and Nutrition Security (FNS) definition, by the European Commission

"Ensuring that everybody is able to access sufficient, sustainable, affordable, healthy and nutritious food in the short and long term"

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Future proof European food system

- Sustainable
- Resilient
- Responsible
- Diverse
- Competitive
- Inclusive

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FOOD 2030 Research & Innovation Priorities

- Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets
- Climate smart and environmentally sustainable food systems
- Circularity and resource efficiency of food systems
- Innovation and empowerment of communities

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Barriers

- Fragmented R&I landscape across disciplines & sectors
- Low involvement of citizens, CSOs, users
- Relatively low private sector investment
- Little support for inter-/trans-disciplinary research (RRI)
- More knowledge and awareness needed of the importance of R&I for FNS
- National research call systems with "open calls"

Future proof European food system

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FIT4FOOD2030

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FOOD 2030/FIT4FOOD2030 Approaches

Food Systems Approach

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FOOD 2030/FIT4FOOD2030 Approaches

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) & Open Science

RRI is an inclusive approach to research and innovation (R&I), to ensure that **societal actors work together** during the whole research and innovation process. It aims to **better align** both the **process and outcomes of R&I**, with the **values, needs and expectations of European society**

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FOOD 2030/FIT4FOOD2030 Approaches

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) & Open Science

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Direct outcomes and Food2030 Platform - creating transformative networks

- EU think Tank: linking member states and EC
- Policy Labs: to align R&I policies and programmes
- City Labs: to link to engage with the local stakeholders (students, professionals, educators, young people)

Strengthened R&I Policy Coherence & Alignment

Built Competences on Food Systems R&I and RRI

Raised Awareness in support of initiatives and action plans

Transformed R&I for FNS

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Workpackages

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Policy Labs...In a nutshell

Creating a dialogue between regional and national stakeholders along the FNS value chain, including science, industry and consumers to explore novel ways of policy design

Potential products: Policy briefs, Methodologies, R&I programmes

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City Labs...In a nutshell

Build a community to understand the system

Analyze the system to build the community

- Two parallel developments: city networks and educational modules
- Flexibility and adaptation to the local context
- Organic growth

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Policy Labs
Focused on national level

City Labs
Focused on city/ regional level

Strengthened R&I Policy Coherence & Alignment (including increased investment)

Built Competences on Food Systems R&I and RRI

Raised Awareness in support of FIT4FOOD initiatives and action plans

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Four phases

Phase 1. Actor identification & mobilisation, visioning and system understanding (M1-12) - to identify and mobilise relevant actors, unite visions, and increase understand of barriers and opportunities for transforming the current system

Phase 2. Developing roadmaps (M10-16) - to develop transformation agendas by identifying showcases in food systems R&I and exploring potential breakthroughs; activities take place successively within City Labs, Policy Labs and EU Think Tank

Phase 3. Action planning and training (M16-36) - to implement transformation agendas; action planning and training carried out in different parts of the platform (City Labs and Policy Labs)

Phase 4. Scaling up & continuity (M26-36) - to expand the 7 Policy Labs and 7 City Labs across Europe to 10 and 14 resp.

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FIT4FOOD2030 Labs

City labs:

- Amsterdam, The Netherlands
- Milan, Italy
- Budapest, Hungary
- Barcelona, Spain
- Athens, Greece
- Sofia, Bulgaria
- Tartu, Estonia

Policy labs:

- The Netherlands
- Italy
- Hungary
- Norway
- Romania
- Flanders (Belgium)

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Lab Communities of Practices

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Communities of Practices

A community formed around a shared domain of interest to generate innovative, creative solutions and practices

When/Why do they work?

- Intrinsically motivated members
- Stimulate the imagination of participants, that is they promote thinking 'outside the box'
- Flexible and continuously adapt
- Collaborative relationships and mutual norms between its members

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FIT4FOOD2030 Communities of Practices

FIT4FOOD2030 Consortium

- Supporting research about the food system: trends, showcases and breakthroughs
- Communications
- Ongoing monitoring

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FIT4FOOD2030 Consortium

15 Consortium Partners & associated networks

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Stakeholder analysis template

Stakeholder:							
Stakeholder category		Power		High	Interest		High
				Low			Low
	Beneficiary	Stakeholder contact data					
	Potential supporter						
	Potential antagonist						
Why is it necessary to involve this stakeholder? Which of the labs aims - or part of the vision - does this help realize?				What is the likely response of the stakeholder to this idea?			
Log for contact with the stakeholder							

Persona template

NAME :

DRAWING

AGE :

PROFESSION :

EDUCATION :

HOMETOWN :

FAMILY :

HOBBIES :

GENERAL INTERESTS :

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS/MEANS/MEDIA :

LIFE MOTTO :

A DAY IN LIFE OF... :

Food system transformation visioning sample pictures

Food system elements

Food system challenges

Food system opportunities

Meditation template

Please close your eyes. Take some time to find an erect posture on your chair with two feet on the ground. Feel your heartbeat and breath. Follow this for a little while.

Now imagine your name is Lara. You, Lara, are going to participate in a City Lab event; however, you are not aware of that yet. Take a look at yourself first. What do you, as Lara, look like? What kind of hair do you have, your clothes, and your posture?

One day, as Lara, you become aware of the existence of the FIT4FOOD2030 City Lab. How will this be communicated to you? What kind of communicative means is used and what is the message? Try to visualize this. What does it do to you to become aware of the City Lab's existence and the event? What does it trigger in you? Will this incite some actions, like searching for stuff on the NET or contacting friends or family? Anything else?

A few days after your 'City Lab awareness' creation moment, so to say, the day has come that you go to the Lab in person. Imagine the location, what does it look like? How will you arrive there and how do you enter the place? What does it look like inside? And who do you see? Who are the other City Lab visitors? And what do the organizers look like? What are they like and how do you recognize them? Look at the space more closely. What physical objects do you see? What kind of objects are present in the space? What kind of materials are they made of? And then, how does the City Lab event start? What is it like? What do you hear? What kind of activities do you undertake and with who? What is it about? How long does it take? And how does it feel for you to participate?

How does the event end? When do you decide to leave and go home? Will you go home? What happens once you have left? What happens to you the day after the event? And a week after it?

..... Take some time to store the pictures you have seen. Come back to this room, feel where you are..... and open your eyes.

Dynamic Learning Agenda – learning diary template

Use one page per challenge/learning question

Challenge/learning question:	
Date for first formulating this challenge/question:	
System analysis: Where in the system does the challenge emerge?	
How can the challenge be overcome? Which resources exist for this?	
How can I/we contribute to this?	
And finally: How was it solved?	
Date for being solved:	